

A case of keratomycosis caused by *Curvularia spicifera* (previously *Bipolaris spicifera*) and review of the literature

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Summary

Fungal keratitis is considered to be an important cause of visual impairment. We present a case of a-post-injury keratitis in a 29-year old male. Upon admission he presented with decreased visual acuity and a corneal ulcer. From the corneal tissue culture, *Curvularia spicifera* (formerly *Bipolaris spicifera*) was isolated and the identification was confirmed by molecular methods. The patient was treated with antifungal agents unsuccessfully, and keratoplasty was performed.

To our knowledge this is the first case of *Bipolaris* keratomycosis reported in Greece and is indicative of the importance of early diagnosis for a favorable outcome.

Key words

keratomycosis, *Bipolaris*, dematiaceous fungi

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Introduction

Fungal keratitis represents about 40% of microbial corneal infections in several tropical and subtropical countries and is considered to be one of most important causes of visual impairment. There are more than 100 species of fungi responsible for keratomycosis, among which members of the genus *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium* and *Candida* are considered to be the most common, but, a wide spectrum of dematiaceous fungi is also implicated. Although fungal keratitis is not as common as bacterial and viral keratitis, it still remains an important cause of ocular morbidity mostly in outdoor workers in the tropics, as these pathogens are widespread in the environment and can be found in soil, wood, and decomposing plant debris. Therefore, the rural population tends to be more vulnerable than the urban one to mycotic keratitis, and the same applies to males compared to females^{1,2}.

Bipolaris is a large genus of dematiaceous hyphomycetes, being anamorphs of the ascomycetous genera *Cochliobolus* and the former *Pseudocochliobolus* including a number of significant plant pathogens with worldwide distribution. The species considered to be pathogenic in humans are *B. spicifera*, *B. hawaiiensis*, *B. australiensis* and *B. papendorfi*. Concerning *Bipolaris* spp keratitis, cases reported in the literature are few²⁻⁵. We report a case of *Curvularia spicifera* (new name for *B. spicifera*) keratitis in an immunocompetent patient which, to our knowledge, is the first case reported in Greece.

Case history

The patient, a 29-year old livestock farmer, resident of a Greek urban area presented to the local ophthalmologist complaining of pain, redness, impaired vision, and a sense of foreign body in the left eye over the last few days. Although he could not recall a specific injury, he was certain that the symptoms had started while working outdoors. From his medical history, gastroesophageal reflux disease and allergic asthma were reported, for which no systematic medication was needed. The ophthalmologist removed a splinter from the patient's left eye and a combination of antibiotics and corticosteroids was prescribed, specifically tobramycin/dexamethasone eye drops three times a day, judging at that time that there was no need for further laboratory examination. A week later, he was reexamined by the ophthalmologist, but no signs of improvement were observed, and he was advised to continue with the same treatment for two more weeks. Five days after the second visit, the patient's condition was deteriorating and this time he decided to seek advice at the local hospital where he was admitted. Upon admission, swab samples from the cornea were taken and the treatment changed to moxifloxacin and tobramycin eye drops every hour, and atropine 1% eye drops twice a day. Following laboratory examination, fungal keratitis, probably due to a hyphomycete, was suspected. For that reason, voriconazole eye drops 1% per hour and fluconazole 100 mg per os twice a day were, additionally, administered. Despite treatment

modification the patient's condition was still deteriorating, leading to spontaneous corneal perforation six days after his admission. Thus, the local hospital recommended transportation to a tertiary hospital with the ability of corneal transplantation, if necessary.

The patient presented to our hospital, 18 days from his first visit to the local ophthalmologist. On the admission day, visual acuity was observed to be reduced to the level of moving hand perception. Slit-lamp examination showed a purulent corneal ulcer near the optic axis without the presence of hypopyon, abundant secretions, athalamia, and conjunctival hyperemia on his left eye (Figure 1). The treatment was changed to amikacin and vancomycin eye drops four times a day, voriconazole 1% eye drops every hour in order to achieve local control of the infection. Furthermore, voriconazole (200 mg) twice a day and moxifloxacin (400 mg) once a day were administered intravenously to prevent intraocular dispersion of the fungus.

However, due to the progressive corneal melt and perforation of the ulcer, therapeutic penetrating keratoplasty was performed in order to remove the af-

fected cornea along with the fungus, and restore integrity of the ocular wall. Briefly, a 9 mm trephination of the patient's cornea, including both the pathological area as well as the optic zone of the cornea, was performed under general anesthesia. A slightly larger (i.e. 9.5 mm) corneal graft was trephined from a healthy donor and sutured on the cornea of the patient. The excised corneal section was sent for microbiological and histological examination.

Four days after uneventful keratoplasty, the patient was discharged with instructions to continue treatment with dexamethasone (0.1%)/chloramphenicol (0.5%) eye drops five times a day, voriconazole (1%) eye drops five times a day, cyclopentolate (1%) eye drops three times a day, and methylprednisolone (16 mg) two tablets/day per os, for two days, and then 1 tablet/day, until his next visit. Two months later, he was re-evaluated. His optical acuity was 1/10 and the transplant status was excellent, i.e. transparent and without any signs of recurrence (Figure 2). Twelve months after surgery visual acuity had reached 8/10 and the transplant status was unchanged.

Figure 1 (A) Side view of the eye showing the absence of anterior chamber (athalamia) due to perforation. (B) Slitlamp image showing the perforated ulcer reaching from the inferonasal periphery the para-central area of the cornea, along with moderate conjunctival hyperemia.

Figure 2 (A) Transparent corneal graft sutured in place by 16 single sutures, (B) Side image, showing the restored anterior chamber being deep.

During the operation, the corneal tissue was sent for microscopy, culture, and susceptibility testing. The tissue was inoculated deep into Sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) with chloramphenicol (0,05g) and gentamycin (0,05g). The initial Gram stain revealed plenty of neutrophils and the microscopic examination of the 15 % KOH wet mount showed branching, phaeoid septate hyphae, suggestive of pheohyphomycotic keratitis (Figure 3). White, cottony colonies began to appear on culture media after 48 hours, and at 72 hours the front surface of the culture showed gray to blackish-brown colonies while the reverse revealed brown-black pigmentation. Lactophenol cotton blue mount of the colonies showed dark pigmented, branched, septate hyphae, and multicelled, smooth-walled, ellipsoidal, conidia with 5-6 thick transverse septa (Figure 4). Thus, the fungus was identified as *Bipolaris spp* and was sent for further molecular identification. The amplification and sequencing of the internal transcribed spacer 1 (ITS1) region of the fungal ribosomal DNA confirmed the phenotypical identification of the genus and further the species was identified as *Curvularia spicifera* (Gen Bank Accession Number: MW229245), formerly *Bipolaris spicifera* according to the most recent phylogenetic studies⁶. Antifungal susceptibility testing (AFST) was performed, using an agar diffusion method by MIC (minimum inhibitory concentration) strips (E-test, bioMerieux SA, France) and according to manufacturer's instructions. MICs found, were: amphotericin B 1.5 µg/mL, itraconazole 32 µg/mL and voriconazole 0.023 µg/mL.

Discussion

The dematiaceous fungi are a large and heterogenous group of filamentous molds sharing as a common characteristic the presence of brown melanin or melanin-like pigments in the cell walls of their hyphae or conidia, or both. In 2012, the genus *Bipolaris* underwent taxonomic revisions based on molecular phylogenetic studies, wherein *Bipolaris* human pathogens have now been shifted to the genus *Curvularia*⁶. *Bipolaris* species are usually considered contaminants in clinical specimens, although a few species can cause human infections, with *B. spicifera* and *B. hawaiiensis* being the most frequent in human clinical samples. They are often responsible for invasive sinusitis and peritonitis, and they can, also, affect the brain and lung tissue causing subcutaneous phaeohyphomycosis and disseminated infections. Ophthalmologic manifestations include keratitis, endophthalmitis or even optic neuropathy².

Satpathy et al⁷, conducted a retrospective study

(2001-2016) which included 218 cases of mycotic keratitis caused by *Bipolaris spp* in north India. Data are collective, therefore there are no details reported for each case separately. Farias et al⁸, evaluated 187 patients treated for corneal ulcers and in 56/187 the causative agent was found to be a mold. *Bipolaris spp* was detected in only one of these cases but no further information about this case was available.

On the other hand, 11 cases of *Bipolaris spp* keratitis with known background are published worldwide, so far^{3,5,9,10-17}. The most common species was *B. hawaiiensis* (*Curvularia hawaiiensis*) with five cases⁹⁻¹³, followed by *B. spicifera*¹⁵⁻¹⁷ with three cases, *B. australiensis* (*Curvularia australiensis*)^{3,14} with two cases and *B. oryzae* (*Curvularia oryzae*) with one case reported.⁵ A review of the literature is presented in Table 1. Most cases come from India, a total of seven cases in specific, and the remaining four cases come from Australia, Brazil, China and Thailand. India is a country with diverse geographical features and climatic conditions. Thus, mycotic keratitis is attributed not only to the temperature and humidity of the environment, but also to the wind and harvest of crops which are responsible for ocular trauma.⁷

The first case of *B. hawaiiensis* keratitis has been reported 22 years ago, by Anandi et al.⁹ It concerned a male patient with leprosy and keratitis caused after injury, and his visual acuity did not improve despite the treatment with nystatin ointment. An interesting case of bilateral *B. hawaiiensis* keratomycosis is reported by Gopalakrishnan et al.,¹⁰ in a patient once again with leprosy, and is considered to be the only case in the literature of bilateral infection of the corneal, treated topically with ketoconazole and, although it was resolved, thick corneal opacities remained in both eyes. Bashir et al.¹¹ reported a case of *B. hawaiiensis* keratitis due to trauma, with delayed diagnosis, which led to endophthalmitis that required evisceration. During the last years, medical management has improved. Chaidaroon et al.¹² reported a case where an outdoor worker with glaucoma, presented with keratitis by *B. hawaiiensis* after eye injury. The patient did not respond to treatment with nystatin and fluconazole, and his visual acuity was restored by keratoplasty. The most recent published case, concerning *B. hawaiiensis* keratitis comes from Yangzes et al.¹³ Patient was an immunocompetent farmer with corneal ulcer after injury. The hypopyon did not resolve with the initial treatment including natamycin and moxifloxacin, but responded well when amphotericin B was injected intracamerally, which obviated the need for penetrating keratoplasty.

B. australiensis was the cause of two cases of keratomycosis in the literature. The first one, reported in

Figure 3 (A) Light microscopy of the cornea tissue, Gram stain (x1000), (B) wet mount with 15 % KOH (x100).

Figure 4 (A) Culture on SDA, (B) reverse side on SDA, (C) lactophenol cotton blue mount (x400).

Australia by Durkin et al,¹⁴ was considered to be spontaneous, but the immunological status of the patient was doubtful, due to alcoholism and pneumonia. In Australia, mycotic keratitis is very rare because the dry climate renders the environment unsuitable for fungal growth. The patient received natamycin with positive outcome. The second case comes from India, by Pai et al,³ and refers to an immunocompetent patient with corneal ulcer following cow tail injury, who responded well to the topical therapy with natamycin and ketoconazole.

There is only one case in the literature of keratitis caused by *B. oryzae*, reported by Wang et al,⁵ which involves a farmer with ocular infection after diesel-oil splashed into his eye from a farming machine, who was successfully treated with combination of keratoplasty, and antifungal treatment, including itraconazole, amphotericin B and topical fluconazole.

Keratitis caused by *B. spicifera* is mentioned in three different cases in the literature with ours being the

forth. First was described in a case by Hemashettar et al,¹⁵ in a middle-aged man. It concerned patient's right eye and he was treated with atropine ointment, econazole cream and Vitamin C tablets and at the time of discharge the ulcer was completely healed.

Saha et al,¹⁶ described a case of keratitis in a female patient with no history of trauma or underlying disease, where treatment with natamycin, nystatin, itraconazole and diamox improved the condition, but keratoplasty was additionally performed due to thick corneal opacity. The third case concerned a male patient who suffered an eye injury while cutting sugarcane and is described by Patil et al.¹⁷ Patient was treated with natamycin and atropine and the infiltration was resolved.

The latest case report in the literature concerned a 29 year-old male patient who developed *Bipolaris spp* keratitis after photorefractive keratectomy. Patient was treated with voriconazole and amphotericin B eye drops, and had a positive outcome.¹⁸

In 2014, the ESCMID (European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases) and ECMM (European Confederation of Medical Mycology) issued joint clinical guidelines for the diagnosis and management of systemic phaeohyphomycosis.¹⁹ Treatment recommendations include: “topical agents, such as natamycin (5%) and topical amphotericin B (0.15-0.3%) which are the most commonly used, with or without topical azoles (1%), for at least four weeks to several months, with strength of recommendation grade A and, quality of evidence level II (recommendation AII). Topical azoles alone, especially itraconazole and voriconazole (1%) can also be used (recommendation BIII). Severe and refractory cases require administration of oral azoles and usually surgery, including penetrating and lamellar keratoplasty (recommendation BIII). An intracorneal injection of voriconazole (1%) as salvage therapy has been efficient in patients not responding to topical and systemic therapy and is marginally supported (recommendation CIII)”. The difficulty in fungal identification and treatment, as well as in the disease management in general, remains crucial and challenging. Early treatment is vital, as it helps to reduce corneal scarring and visual impairment, but also prevents severe complications.^{2,20} In the case of the here described patient, corneal transplantation was successful, and the visual acuity improved, despite the initial failure of the pharmaceutical treatment, which points out the significance of early diagnosis for less complications and a more favorable outcome.

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Declaration of Interest

The authors have no conflict of interest.

Table 1 Reported cases of *Bipolaris* spp keratitis in the literature.

Species	Year	Localization	Gender	Age	Injury	Health status	Outcome	Reference
<i>B. spicifera</i>	2021	left eye	male	29	yes	immunocompetent	Keratoplasty	present
<i>Bipolaris</i> spp	2021	left eye	male	29	photorefractive keratectomy	immunocompetent	Resolved	18
<i>B. hawaiiensis</i>	2019	left eye	male	55	yes	immunocompetent	Resolved	13
<i>B. australiensis</i>	2017	left eye	male	59	yes	immunocompetent	Resolved	3
<i>B. oryzae</i>	2016	right eye	male	54	diesel oil splashed	immunocompetent	Resolved	5
<i>B. hawaiiensis</i>	2016	left eye	male	63	yes	ocular hypertension	penetrating keratoplasty	12
<i>B. spicifera</i>	2011	right eye	male	38	yes		Resolved	17
<i>B. hawaiiensis</i>	2009	left eye	male	50	yes	immunocompetent	evisecretion	11
<i>B. australiensis</i>	2008	right eye	male	29	no	alcohol abuse	Resolved	14
<i>B. spicifera</i>	2005	left eye	female	28	no	immunocompetent	Keratoplasty	16
<i>B. hawaiiensis</i>	2003	bilateral	male	45	yes, only the right eye	borderline leprosy	thick opacities in both eyes	10
<i>B. spicifera</i>	1992	right eye	male	middle aged	no	leprosy under treatment	Resolved	15
<i>B. hawaiiensis</i>	1988	right eye	male	47	yes	borderline leprosy	Opacities	9

Περίληψη

Περιστατικό μυκητιασικής κερατίτιδας από *Curvularia spicifera* (*Bipolaris spicifera*) και ανασκόπηση της βιβλιογραφίας

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Η μυκητιασική κερατίτιδα αποτελεί σημαντικό αίτιο οφθαλμικής νοσηρότητας. Η περίπτωση που περιγράφεται αφορά έναν νέο, ανοσοεπαρκή ασθενή που εμφάνισε μυκητιασική κερατίτιδα μετά από τραυματισμό. Ο ασθενής προσήλθε με μειωμένη οπτική οξύτητα και κατά την εισαγωγή του διαπιστώθηκε έλκος κερατοειδούς. Η καλλιέργεια του κερατοειδούς ανέδειξε φαιοϋφομύκητα ο οποίος ταυτοποιήθηκε με συμβατικές και μοριακές μεθόδους ως *Curvularia spicifera* (παλαιότερη ονομασία *Bipolaris spicifera*). Ο ασθενής έλαβε αγωγή με αντιμυκητικά φάρμακα χωρίς όμως ικανοποιητική ανταπόκριση με αποτέλεσμα να χρειαστεί κερατοπλαστική. Εξ όσων γνωρίζουμε, πρόκειται για την πρώτη περίπτωση μυκητιασικής κερατίτιδας από *Curvularia spicifera* που περιγράφεται στην Ελλάδα και σκιαγραφεί την σπουδαιότητα της έγκαιρης διάγνωσης προκειμένου η έκβαση να είναι ευνοϊκή.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

Κερατομύκωση, *Bipolaris*, *Curvularia spicifera*, fungal keratitis, φαιοϋφομύκητες

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